

The Influence of Influencer Credibility and Electronic Word of Mouth on Purchase Intention of Grace and Glow Product Among Students in Malang City

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the influence of influencer credibility and electronic word of mouth on purchase intention of grace and glow product among students in malang city. This research used an explanatory method with a quantitative approach. Data collection was conducted through Data were collected through online questionnaires using purposive sampling, targeting 69 respondents from state university students in Malang. Multiple linear regression analysis was conducted using SPSS version 25. The results showed that both influencer credibility and electronic word of mouth had a partial and significant effect on purchase intention. Meanwhile, the regression results indicate that both variables also have a positive and significant influence on consumers' purchase intention toward Grace and Glow products.

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The findings conclude that influencer credibility and electronic word of mouth significantly shape consumer purchase intention for Grace and Glow. The company was advised to continue collaborating with credible influencers and encourage positive review content to strengthen consumer purchase intention

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of technology has facilitated various aspects of human life, including shopping activities. According to the Laporan Data (2023) report, in 2023 as many as 64.4% of the global population, or around 5.16 billion people, had access to the internet. This creates significant opportunities for brands to engage with consumers online, particularly through social media platforms such as Instagram. This shows that Instagram has become an effective medium to build engagement with consumers, especially in the beauty and personal care sector.

Public awareness of the importance of body and skincare has also grown rapidly. The Zap Beauty Index (2023) further shows that 96.8% of Indonesian women have used local skincare brands, with 19% exclusively using local products. On the other hand, 81% also use international skincare brands, though only 3.2% use them exclusively. This indicates that local beauty brands have a strong opportunity to expand through digital marketing strategies, especially on Instagram.

One prominent example is Grace and Glow, a local bodycare brand established in 2021 by Zalika Aishah. Grace and Glow has successfully attracted young consumers by highlighting natural ingredients, elegant packaging, and influencer collaborations. The brand's popular product, the Black Opium variant of its hair mist, gained significant attention in 2022 and remains a consumer favorite compared to other brands like Makarizo. Moreover, Grace and Glow ranked second in the "Top Brand Hall of Fame for Body Wash" according to Kompas (Cemara, 2023), demonstrating its competitiveness with international brands.

A key marketing strategy of Grace and Glow is the use of influencer credibility. Wiedmann & von Mettenheim (2020) explained that attractiveness, trustworthiness, and expertise are essential elements for influencers to be perceived as credible. Savitri & Fauji (2021) found that e-WOM enhances product success through consumer testimonials and online communities. Similarly, Nurjanah & Limanda (2024) argued that positive online reviews shape consumer perceptions, while Khoirudin & Marginingsih

(2025) confirmed that e-WOM has a positive and significant impact on purchase intention. Thus, the combination of credible influencers and strong e-WOM becomes a powerful driver of consumer purchase interest.

This research focuses on students in Malang City, as Generation Z represents a highly strategic market segment for beauty products. According to Portal Malang (2025), there are 60 universities in the city, accommodating hundreds of thousands of students from across Indonesia. Gen Z, as digital-native consumers, are highly active on social media and tend to rely on reviews and influencer recommendations before purchasing products online. Previous studies often examined influencer credibility and e-WOM separately, but this research aims to explore the combined influence of both factors on purchase intention. By taking Grace and Glow as the case study, this research is expected to provide insights into the effectiveness of digital marketing in the beauty industry, particularly in attracting Gen Z consumers through influencers and e-WOM.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Marketing

According to Tjiptono & Diana (2020), marketing is a process involving the creation, distribution, promotion, and pricing of goods, services, and ideas. It can be concluded that marketing is not just about selling products, but involves a series of systematic processes to meet consumer needs and create value for them. Another opinion by Laksana (2019) is that marketing is a meeting between sellers and buyers to conduct transactions of goods or services. In other words, marketing is the process where sellers and buyers meet to conduct transactions of goods or services.

Marketing Communication

Firmansyah (2019) explain that marketing communication is defined as a tool used by companies to inform, persuade, and remind consumers, both directly and indirectly, about the products and brands offered. Another opinion by Kotler et al., (2016), marketing communication aims to convey messages to the public, especially to target consumers regarding the presence of products in the market. Thus, the essence of marketing communication is as a means for companies to inform, persuade, and remind consumers about the products and brands being sold.

Influencer Credibility

According to Shimp & Andrews (2018), who explain that fundamentally, credibility can be defined as the willingness to trust someone. If the information from the influencer is perceived as credible, it will affect the psychological condition of the influencer's followers by accepting any information provided. There are 3 indicators of influencer credibility, are as follows: 1) Attractiveness, 2) Trustworthiness, 3) Expertise.

Electronic Word of Mouth (E-WOM)

According to Litvin et al in Ayesha et al (2022), electronic word of mouth is an informal communication that occurs with customers regarding the use or features of certain products and services through the internet. Goyette et al in Prihartini & Damastuti (2022) mention that there are 3 indicators in the electronic word of mouth variable, as follows: 1) Intensity, 2) Valence of opinion, 3) Content.

Purchase Intention

According to Kotler et al (2016) state that purchase intention is a consumer behavior that arises in response to an object reflecting the consumer's desire to make a purchase. There are 4 indicators to measure the purchase intention variable (Priansa, 2017), namely : 1) Transactional interest, 2) Referential interest, 3) Preferential interest, 4) Exploratory interest.

Hypothesis Formulation

H1 : It is suspected that Influencer Credibility variable partially has a significant effect on the Purchase Intention variable.

Research conducted by Suryati et al (2024), which found that the credibility of the influencer partially has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. Similarly, Lumbantoruan & Marwansyah (2023), revealed that the credibility of influencers has a positive and significant impact on consumer purchase intention.

H2 : It is suspected that Electronic Word of Mouth variable partially has a significant effect on the Purchase Intention variable.

Research conducted by Khoirudin & Marginingsih (2025), who discovered that Electronic word-of-mouth has a positive influence on purchase intention.

H3 : It is suspected that Influencer Credibility and Electronic Word of Mouth simultaneously have a significant effect on the variable of Purchase Intention.

Research conducted by Putri & Wulandari (2024) state that the credibility of influencers and electronic word of mouth have a positive and significant effect on purchase intention in their research.

III. METHOD

This research applies a quantitative method based on the identified problems and objectives. Quantitative research is a systematic scientific study of parts and phenomena as well as the causal relationships between them (Abdullah et al., 2021). The research method used is a survey. The Survey Method is used in evaluations to systematically, factually, and accurately illuminate the facts and characteristics of a particular population or area (Abdullah et al., 2021). This study aims to analyze the influence of influencer credibility and electronic word of mouth on consumer purchase interest in Grace and Glow products among students at state universities in Malang City.

The population in this study is categorized as infinite, indicating the presence of a target population that is unbounded or cannot be quantitatively determined (Amruddin et al., 2022). The population in this study is students from state universities in Malang City who follow the Instagram account Grace and Glow (@graceandglow.id), with a sample of 69 respondents selected through purposive sampling which is the selection of samples based on specific characteristics (Sugiyono, 2017). The consideration referred to is the criterion applied in this research, namely students of state universities in the city of Malang who follow the Instagram account Grace and Glow (@graceandglow.id).

Data were collected using a questionnaire that was distributed online via Google Forms to students from state universities in Malang City who follow the Instagram account Grace and Glow (@graceandglow.id), measured using a five-point Likert scale. The research instrument was tested for validity and reliability, followed by descriptive analysis, classical assumption testing, multiple linear regression analysis, coefficient of determination testing, and hypothesis testing.

IV. RESULTS

Validity Test

According to Abdullah et al (2021) stated that validity is accuracy and precision, or in the language commonly used in the research world, it is valid or legitimate. In this study, the total number of samples (n) is 69 respondents, and the degrees of freedom (df) are calculated using the formula $df = n - 2$, resulting in $df = 69 - 2 = 67$. With $df = 67$ and a significance level of 0.05 (5%), the critical r table value is 0.1997. The following are the results of the validity test using IBM SPSS Statistics 25:

Table 1. Validity Test Results

Variables	Item	r _{count}	r _{table}	Sig	Results
Influencer Credibility (X1)	X1.1	0,737	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	X1.2	0,756	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	X1.3	0,742	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	X1.4	0,750	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	X1.5	0,745	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	X1.6	0,754	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	X1.7	0,807	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	X1.8	0,762	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	X1.9	0,785	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	X1.10	0,702	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	X1.11	0,715	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	X1.12	0,784	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	X2.1	0,798	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	X2.2	0,693	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	X2.3	0,746	0,1997	0,000	Valid

Variables	Item	r _{count}	r _{table}	Sig	Results
Electronic Word of Mouth (X2)	X2.4	0,803	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	X2.5	0,746	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	X2.6	0,710	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	X2.7	0,803	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	X2.8	0,810	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	X2.9	0,802	0,1997	0,000	Valid
Purchase Intention (Y)	Y1.1	0,821	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	Y1.2	0,702	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	Y1.3	0,765	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	Y1.4	0,741	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	Y1.5	0,750	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	Y1.6	0,821	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	Y1.7	0,795	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	Y1.8	0,751	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	Y1.9	0,801	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	Y1.10	0,776	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	Y1.11	0,738	0,1997	0,000	Valid
	Y1.12	0,831	0,1997	0,000	Valid

Source : Processed Data (2025)

Based on Table 1, all correlation coefficients or r_{count} have a value greater than 0.1997, so this shows that all items used as measuring instruments for the Influencer Credibility variable (X1) Electronic Word of Mouth (X2) and Purchase Interest (Y) are declared valid.

Reliability Test

Ghozali (2021: 61) argues that, "Reliability is actually a tool for measuring a questionnaire which is an indicator of a variable or construct. A questionnaire is said to be reliable or reliable if someone's answer to a question is consistent or stable over time". A construct or variable is said to be reliable if it provides a Cronbach Alpha value > 0.70, nunnally in Ghozali (2021: 62). The following are the results of the reliability test using IBM SPSS Statistics 25:

Table 2. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach Alpha	Standart	Information
Influencer Credibility	0,931	0,7	Reliable
Electronic Word of Mouth	0,913	0,7	Reliable
Purchase Intention	0,939	0,7	Reliable

Source : Processed Data (2025)

Based on Table 2, it shows that all items used as a measuring tool for the Influencer Credibility variable (X1) are declared reliable because the Cronbach's Alpha value obtained is greater than 0.7, which is 0.931, while for the Electronic Word of Mouth

variable (X2) it is declared reliable because the Crombach's Alpha value obtained is greater than 0.7, which is 0.913 and the Purchase Interest variable (Y) is declared reliable because the Cronbach's Alpha obtained is greater than 0.7, which is 0.939.

Normality Test

According to Ghozali (2018), the normality test aims to determine whether the distribution of a data follows or approaches a normal distribution, namely the distribution of data with a bell shape. The normality of the data can be assessed visually through graphs, if the data points in a normal probability plot lie close to the diagonal line and follow its direction, or if the histogram shows a bell-shaped curve, then the regression model can be considered to meet the normality assumption. The normality test results in this study are shown in the image below:

Figure 1. P-Plot Normality Graph

Figure 2. Histogram of Normality Test

Source : IBM SPSS Statistic 25, Processed Data (2025)

Source : IBM SPSS Statistic 25, Processed Data (2025)

Based on the figure 1 & 2 normality test results, the data points are spread around and follow the direction of the diagonal line in the normality plot, and the histogram shows a normal distribution pattern. This indicates that the linear regression model in this study meets the normality assumption.

Multicollinearity Test

According to Ghozali (2018), Multicollinearity test is needed to determine whether there are independent variables that have similarities between independent variables in a model. Similarity between independent variables will result in a very strong correlation. To determine whether there are symptoms of multicollinearity, it can be seen from the magnitude of the Tolerance and VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) values. The results of the multicollinearity test in this study can be seen in table as follows:

Table 3. Multicollinearity Test Result

Model	Collinearity Statistics		Information
	Tolerance	VIF	
Influencer Credibility	0,108	9,234	There is no multicollinearity
Electronic Word of Mouth	0,108	9,234	

Source : Processed Data (2025)

Based on the table 3, it can be seen that there is a tolerance value that meets the requirements with a tolerance limit of $0.108 > 0.10$ or $VIF 9.234 < 10.00$. So the analysis shows that there is no multicollinearity and also shows that each independent variable and the dependent variable are not interdependent.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity tests the variance of residuals from one observation period to another. One way to approach heteroscedasticity is to look at the scatter plot graph between the predicted value of the dependent variable and its residuals. If there are points forming a certain regular pattern such as wavy, widening then narrowing then heteroscedasticity has occurred. If the dots spread above and below or around the number 0 without forming a certain pattern, heteroscedasticity does not occur (Ghozali, 2018). The following are the results of the heteroscedasticity test in this study using the graphical method:

Figure 3. Heteroscedasticity Test Result

Source : IBM SPSS Statistic 26, Processed Data (2025)

From the figure 3, it is known that the dots that constitute the data in the study spread randomly and do not form a certain pattern. In addition, the points spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis, so it can be stated that all data in the study are free from heteroscedasticity problems.

Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis is used to determine whether there is an influence of the independent variables (Influencer Credibility and Electronic Word of Mouth) on the dependent variable (Purchase Intention) and test the correctness of the hypothesis proposed in this study (Ghozali, 2018). The following presents the results of data processing using IBM SPSS Statistics 25:

Table 4. Multiple Regression Analysis Result

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	
	B	Std. Error
Constant	0,343	1,847
Influencer Credibility (X1)	0,550	0,127
Electronic Word of Mouth (X2)	0,583	0,163

Source : Processed Data (2025)

Based on the table 4, the results of multiple linear regression analysis tests can be known linear regression equation as follows:

$$Y = 0,343 + 0.550 X1 + 0.583 X2 + e$$

Based on the multiple linear regression equation, it can be explained as follows:

1. The constant value $a = 0.343$ means that if the Influencer Credibility (X1) and Electronic Word of Mouth (X2) variables are assumed to be zero, then the Purchase Interest (Y) variable has the same constant value of 0.343.
2. The regression coefficient value of the Influencer Credibility variable (X1) of 0.550 shows a positive value. This value illustrates that the influencer credibility variable has a unidirectional influence on purchase intention. The regression coefficient value indicates that if the influencer credibility variable increases by one unit, while the electronic word of mouth variable (X2) is considered to be zero, the purchase intention variable (Y) will increase by 0.550.
3. The regression coefficient value of the Electronic Word of Mouth (X2) variable of 0.583 shows a positive value. This value illustrates that the electronic word of mouth variable (X2) has a unidirectional influence on purchase intention. The regression coefficient value indicates that if the electronic word of mouth variable increases by one unit, while the influencer credibility variable is considered to be zero, the purchase intention variable will increase by 0.583.
4. The error value (e) obtained from the regression equation is 1.847, which means that if the smaller the error value, it shows the level of accuracy in predicting the dependent variable.

These results mean that influencer credibility has a stronger influence on purchase intention than electronic word of mouth. In marketing, this shows that building trust through credible, expert, and attractive influencers is more effective in encouraging consumers to buy the product. For example, collaborating with influencers who align with the brand image and have strong engagement with their followers can increase purchase interest and loyalty more than just relying on online reviews or customer discussions.

Coefficient of Determination

According to Sujarweni (2015) the coefficient of determination, which is denoted by Rsquare, is an important measure in regression. Determination (Rsquare) reflects the ability of the dependent variable. The purpose of this analysis is to calculate the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The following presents the results of data processing using IBM SPSS Statistics 25:

Table 5. Coefficient of Determination Result (R²)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0,946	0,895	0,891	2,192

Source : Processed Data (2025)

Based on the table 5, the coefficient of determination (R²) shows that the ability of the independent variables (influencer credibility and electronic word of mouth) in a large contribution to the influence of purchase intention is 89.1%. An influence of 10.9% is given by other variables not included in this study.

Partial Test (T test)

Partial Hypothesis Test is an individual partial regression coefficient test used to determine whether the independent variable (X) individually affects the dependent variable (Y). For t table determined with $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%), the number of samples of 69 (n) is with df (degree of freedom) = $(\alpha/2; n-k-1 = 0.05/2; 69-2-1 = 0.025; 66 = 1.66827)$, n is the number of samples and k is the number of independent variables. With this, the result for t table is 1.66827. The following presents the results of data processing using IBM SPSS Statistics 25:

Table 6. Partial Test (T test) Result

Variable	t count	t table	Sig	Sig level	Information
Influencer Credibility	4,320	1,668	0.000	0.05	Significant
Electronic Word of Mouth	3,575	1,668	0.001	0.05	Significant

Source : Processed Data (2025)

Based on the table 6, the t-test results for the Product Display and Shopping Lifestyle variables on Impulse Buying are as follows:

- H1: In the Influencer Credibility variable (X1), the tcount > ttable value is obtained ($4.320 > 1.668$) and sig $0.000 < 0.05$. With these two things it can be said that H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted. This shows that there is a significant positive effect of the Influencer Credibility variable (X1) on the Purchase Intention variable (Y) among student consumers of Grace and Glow products in Malang City.
- H2: In the Electronic Word of Mouth (X2) variable, the tcount > ttable value is obtained ($3.575 > 1.668$) and sig $0.001 < 0.05$. With these two things it can be said that H0 is rejected and H2 is accepted. This shows that there is a significant positive effect of the Electronic Word of Mouth (X2) variable on the Purchase Intention (Y) variable among student consumers of Grace and Glow products in Malang City.

Simultaneous Test (F test)

The simultaneous hypothesis test is used to determine the significant level of influence of the independent variables together (simultaneously) on the dependent variable (Ghozali, 2018). For f table determined with $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%), the number of samples of 69 (n) is with df (degree of freedom) = $(\alpha/2; n-k-1 = 0.05/2; 69-2-1 = 0.025; 66 = 3.14)$, n is the number of samples and k is the number of independent variables. With this, the result for f table is 3.14. The following presents the results of data processing using IBM SPSS Statistics 25:

Table 7. Simultaneous Test (F test) Result

f count	f table	Sig	Significance level	Information
279,819	3.14	0.000	0.05	Significant

Source : Processed Data (2025)

H3: Based on the simultaneous hypothesis test results listed in the table, it can be seen that Fcount > Ftable ($279.819 > 3.14$) and sig $0.000 < 0.05$. So it can be said that H0 is rejected and H3 is accepted. This shows that there is a positive influence of the Influencer Credibility variable (X1) and the Electronic Word of Mouth variable (X2) significantly on the Purchase Interest variable (Y) among student consumers of Grace and Glow products in Malang City.

V. DISCUSSION

1. Influencer Credibility Affects Grace and Glow Consumer Purchase Intention in Malang City

The test results show that influencer credibility significantly affects consumer purchase intention for Grace and Glow products, with t -count $4.320 > 1.668$ and $\text{sig } 0.000 < 0.05$, meaning H1 is accepted. Respondents rated trustworthiness highly (3.67), indicating that they tend to trust and be interested in products recommended by influencers perceived as honest, knowledgeable, and attractive. This finding supports Shimp & Andrews (2018), who emphasize that credibility reflects consumers' willingness to trust information, and is consistent with Putri & Wulandari (2024) and Suryati et al. (2024), who also found that credible influencers positively and significantly increase purchase intention.

2. Electronic Word of Mouth Affects Grace and Glow Consumer Purchase Intention in Malang City

The test results show that electronic word of mouth (e-WOM) significantly influences consumer purchase intention for Grace and Glow products, with t -count $3.575 > 1.668$ and $\text{sig } 0.001 < 0.05$, so H2 is accepted. Respondents rated content indicators highly (3.63), showing that informative reviews, testimonials, and user experiences strongly build trust and interest compared to advertisements. This supports Nurjanah & Limanda (2024), who argue that e-WOM is trusted because it is non-commercial and based on real user experiences, and aligns with studies by Khoirudin & Marginingsih (2025) and Prihantini & Damastuti (2022), which found that quality e-WOM positively and significantly increases purchase intention.

3. Influencer Credibility and Electronic Word of Mouth Affect Grace and Glow Consumer Purchase Intention in Malang City

The test results show that influencer credibility and electronic word of mouth (e-WOM) together have a significant positive effect on purchase intention for Grace and Glow products, with F -count $279.819 > 3.98$ and $\text{sig } 0.000 < 0.05$, so H3 is accepted. Influencer credibility not only directly increases buying interest but also generates positive e-WOM, as trusted influencers encourage consumers to share information. This supports Olmedilla et al. (2016), who noted that credible influencers shape positive e-WOM that drives consumer attention and purchase decisions, and is consistent with Putri & Wulandari (2024) and Khoirudin & Marginingsih (2025), who found that the combination of influencer credibility and e-WOM significantly boosts purchase intention.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the research conducted using a quantitative approach by distributing questionnaires to Generation Z respondents in Malang who are familiar with Grace and Glow products, several stages of analysis were carried out.

1. The first finding shows that influencer credibility has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. This means that when an influencer is perceived as trustworthy, attractive, and knowledgeable, consumers are more likely to trust their recommendations and be interested in purchasing the promoted product. A credible influencer increases consumer confidence and has a strong impact on shaping purchasing behavior.
2. The second finding reveals that electronic word of mouth (e-WOM) also has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. This suggests that consumers are more likely to develop the intention to purchase when they are exposed to positive online reviews, testimonials, and user experiences shared by others. The honest and non-commercial nature of e-WOM plays a critical role in influencing how consumers perceive the product.
3. When examined simultaneously, influencer credibility and e-WOM together have a positive and significant influence on purchase intention. This indicates that the combination of a credible influencer and strong, positive online consumer communication has a substantial impact on increasing consumers' intention to buy Grace and Glow products. Therefore, both factors are crucial in shaping consumer attitudes and decision-making, especially in the context of digital marketing to Generation Z.

VII. SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of research and analysis based on the frequency distribution of questionnaires that have been carried out by researchers, the suggestions given are as follows:

1. Based on the points that become weaknesses in the influencer credibility variable in the descriptive analysis, consumers tend to be interested in influencers who have an image that is aligned with brand identity such as natural beauty, self-confidence, and others. Influencers who have experience in promoting skincare products will be considered more credible. An influencer must also fulfill requirements in delivering product messages such as honesty and transparency. The influencer's credibility is also judged by their skills in delivering clear, creative and engaging messages.
2. Based on the points that are a weakness in the electronic word of mouth variable in the descriptive analysis, Grace and Glow should provide informative content that is easily accessible such as usage tutorials, in-depth reviews from beauty experts, or FAQs about products. Grace and Glow needs to encourage more testimonials from satisfied customers. Grace and glow should also actively respond to comments and reviews to show appreciation and transparency, while addressing complaints quickly to maintain its reputation. Grace and Glow should ensure that pricing details, promos or budgets are clearly available across platforms. Transparent and competitive pricing, which includes an explanation of the product's added value, can reduce potential buyers' hesitation and encourage sales conversions.

3. Based on the findings, it is suggested that Grace and Glow should continue to enhance factors that positively influence consumers' purchase intention. This includes creating engaging marketing campaigns, maintaining consistent product quality, and highlighting the value and benefits of their products in a way that resonates with Gen Z consumers. Moreover, offering promotions, bundling strategies, or loyalty programs can also help increase consumers' motivation and intention to purchase the product.

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